

CASE REPORT

Prune Belly Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

Prune Belly syndrome (PBS) is a rare congenital anomaly of uncertain aetiology almost exclusive to males. PBS may be associated with lower urinary tract obstruction (LUTO) which results in bladder distension and abdominal musculature deficiency. Therefore, early detection of the disease and proper treatment before the renal impairment is important which may require intrauterine intervention like vesicocentesis. We report a case of prune belly syndrome diagnosed at 17 weeks of gestation with USG findings of a single live foetus with anhydramnios, over distended urinary bladder covering almost entire abdominal cavity, bilateral hydronephrosis and single umbilical artery.

INTRODUCTION

Prune belly syndrome (PBS) is known as Eagle-Barrett Syndrome or Obrinsky syndrome is a rare syndrome affecting about 1 in 40,000 births and is characterized by a lack of development of abdominal wall muscles giving the appearance of thin wrinkled skin which appears “prune-like”, skeletal anomalies, and renal anomalies such as dilated bladder, megaureters, and bilateral cryptorchidism¹. The exact aetiology of this disorder is not known but some studies have indicated that there is a possibility of genetic inheritance and possible chromosomal association with Edward and down syndrome². More than 95% of affected cases are of male gender.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 27 year second gravida came for first antenatal scan. Previous pregnancy was completely normal. No significant medical or family history. No H/o drug intake. USG findings revealed a single live foetus of about 17 weeks of gestation with anhydramnios, over distended urinary bladder covering almost entire abdominal cavity, bilateral hydronephrosis and single umbilical artery. Other foetal biometry was normal. All bowel loops were pushed cranially towards liver which indicates that lesion is likely of pelvic origin pushing peritoneal organs upwards. Pregnancy was terminated on request of family members and findings of prune belly syndrome were confirmed as foetus was showing thin wrinkled abdominal wall and large ruptured cystic cavity.

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Image 1 A : Color doppler image showing single umbilical artery B : Grey scale image showing well defined cystic lesion in the abdominal cavity. C: Grey scale image showing bilateral hydronephrosis.

Image 2: Post natal images of the foetus showing thin wrinkled abdominal wall and large ruptured cystic cavity.

DISCUSSION

Prune-belly syndrome or Eagle-Barrett syndrome is a rare congenital anomaly. The etiopathogenesis of PBS is not completely understood. Many theories have been suggested; urinary tract obstruction, genetic deficit, abnormalities of allantois and maldevelopment of the mesoderm. Prune belly syndrome occurs with variable degrees of severity. Those with less severe renal disease may survive infancy, but may have recurrent urinary tract infection or progressive renal insufficiency³. Little or no loss of renal function is seen in some mild cases with a better prognosis. In severe cases, renal dysplasia and oligohydramnios in utero result in pulmonary hypoplasia. These infants may be stillborn or die shortly after birth often due to respiratory distress. Pulmonary,

cardiovascular, gastrointestinal and musculoskeletal abnormalities are also associated with Prune belly syndrome. The clinical manifestations are deficiency of abdominal wall muscles, cryptorchidism in male fetus with genitourinary malformations^{4,5}. Prune belly syndrome is characterized by pulmonary hypoplasia, pneumothorax, oligohydramnios, renal dysplasia, urethral obstruction patent urachus or club feet. Although pulmonary hypoplasia may not be clearly identified in the very early gestational age. Urine production in foetus starts from 8 and 10 weeks of gestation and fetal bladder can be visualized by sonography by 11 weeks of gestation. Therefore the antenatal diagnosis of prune belly syndrome is rarely reported before 11 weeks of gestation^{2,4}. In our case fetus was diagnosed as prune belly syndrome by prenatal abdominal ultrasound at around 17 weeks of gestational age with very large urinary bladder. As renal function compromise is a factor that determines the prognosis, prenatal intervention is needed to preserve renal function and to provide the aqueous environment for lung maturation⁶. Regular monitoring by sonography of the urinary tract and amniotic fluid volume in utero is required with antenatal management of Prune belly syndrome by fetal vesicoamniotic shunting, termination of pregnancy, or early delivery as long as the neonatal viability is achieved. Vesicoamniotic shunt for urinary obstruction can prevent pulmonary hypoplasia and renal dysplasia or even may improve postnatal quality of life. Vesico-centesis for the treatment of fetal megacystis and prune belly syndrome have been reported to reduce the bladder volume without severe complications. This study suggests the importance of the early diagnosis of this congenital anomaly however in our case, pregnancy was terminated upon request of parents. Furthermore, as prompt intervention in second trimester the vesico-centesis with finer needle can be used as an effective treatment modality to relieve the lower urinary tract obstruction to improve the prognosis.

CONCLUSION

Prune-belly syndrome or Eagle-Barrett syndromes is a rare congenital anomaly. Radiologists must be well versed with this anomaly for antenatal diagnosis as early as possible so that timely decision can be made regarding the course of pregnancy, prenatal intervention to preserve renal function and to provide the aqueous environment for lung maturation and post-delivery management based on the severity of the condition.

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